
SPEAKING AS AN INTERACTIVE PROCESS: KINDS OF SPOKEN INTERACTION AS A PART OF THE CLASSROOM PROCESS RELATING TO ALL SKILLS

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Abstract: This article explores speaking as an interactive process and analyzes its interaction with other language skills within the classroom. The significance of interactive speaking and its role in the educational process are discussed, along with various methods teachers can use to develop spoken interaction. The article focuses on how interactive activities can enhance students' speaking skills.

Keywords: Speaking, interactive process, spoken interaction, classroom, language skills, teaching methods, communication, activities

Introduction

Speaking is a crucial skill in the language learning process that often goes unnoticed. The speaking process plays a significant role in enhancing students' verbal abilities, participating in communication, and exchanging ideas. Interactive speaking provides students with the opportunity to develop alongside other skills, such as listening, reading, and writing. The speaking process is not merely about expressing an idea; it encompasses communication and the exchange of ideas, feelings, and opinions. This article examines different types of spoken interaction, their importance in the educational process, and how teachers can implement them effectively.

Main Body

The Role of Speaking as an Interactive Process

Interactive speaking is a process that helps increase students' verbal engagement. In this process, students interact with each other by exchanging ideas, asking questions, and articulating their thoughts. The interactive process enables students to express their views freely, enhancing their social and emotional skills. Furthermore, the interactive speaking process improves students' mutual understanding and increases their attention

span. By listening to each other, students learn to monitor their communication, share thoughts, and embrace new ideas. Thus, interactive speaking not only develops language skills but also enhances social competencies.

Types of Spoken Interaction

1. Dialogues and Conversations:

Natural conversations that occur between students, allowing them to exchange ideas on various topics.

Dialogues enable students to articulate their thoughts, enhance their comprehension skills, and develop social interactions.

2. Role-Playing:

Students actively participate in speaking interactions by taking on different roles. They engage in conversations based on scenarios that mimic real-life situations.

Role-playing helps foster students' creative thinking and strengthens interpersonal communication.

3. Debates:

Students participate in discussions to defend their viewpoints and articulate their positions. This process is highly effective in developing communication skills and allows students to express their opinions clearly.

4. Comparative Analysis:

Students analyze different texts and share their thoughts, comparing and discussing them.

This facilitates understanding various perspectives and creates opportunities for discussion among students.

Organizing Interactive Speaking Activities in the Classroom

In the classroom, teachers need to create a unique environment for students. Interactive speaking activities encourage students to express their opinions, ask questions, and learn from each other. Teachers can employ various activities, such as **group work**, **small group discussions**, and **unconventional games** to enhance student interaction.

Group Work: Students collaborate with each other, which allows them to exchange ideas and fosters cooperative learning.

Small Group Discussions: Students engage in discussions on specific topics within small groups. This process enables them to express their thoughts openly, listen to one another, and propose creative solutions.

Unconventional Games: Teachers can use games to develop spoken interaction. For instance, the "Word Chain" game encourages students to speak more and develop their verbal skills.

Conclusion

Spoken interaction holds significant importance in the educational process, as it aids students in developing valuable knowledge and skills. Interactive speaking allows students to improve their verbal abilities, participate in communication, and enhance mutual understanding. Teachers must effectively utilize spoken interactions and ensure that every student's verbal competence is nurtured.

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